

Operational Interoperability in Digital Clinical Trials: An Exploratory Study

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Abstract. The digitalization of clinical trials has increased the need for reliable data exchange across clinical research informatics systems, trial processes, organizations and research sites. Although interoperability standards such as HL7, FHIR and CDISC provide important technical and syntactic foundations, practitioners continue to encounter operational barriers when data must move across heterogeneous systems and organizational boundaries. This paper examines operational interoperability in digital clinical trials, understood as the practical alignment of technical, syntactic, semantic and organizational/procedural forms of data exchange. Based on seven semi-structured interviews with Swiss-based stakeholders from pharmaceutical companies, service providers, healthcare providers and clinics, the study explores interoperability challenges at three levels: within systems and tasks, vertically across successive clinical trial processes, and horizontally across organizations, sites and countries. The findings show that interoperability problems persist not only because interfaces or standards are missing, but also because standards are unevenly implemented, systems require costly customization, workarounds remain embedded in daily practice, and legal or organizational uncertainty limits cross-site data exchange. The paper contributes a three-level framework for identifying interoperability vulnerabilities in digital clinical trials. Given the small and Swiss-based empirical sample, the study does not claim generalizability but offers an exploratory framework for future comparative and larger-scale research.

Keywords: Clinical Research Informatics, Clinical Trials, Interoperability

1 Introduction

Clinical Research Informatics (CRI) refers to the use of information technologies and systems to support clinical research processes [1]. Its growing adoption reflects the increasing complexity of clinical studies, which involve multiple stakeholders, processes, and data sources across governmental, academic, and private sectors. CRI has therefore become essential for improving the efficiency and quality of clinical research through digitalization [2]. As a subspecialty of biomedical informatics, the field has significantly evolved in recent years and continues to transform clinical research practices [3].

A central challenge in CRI is interoperability. Beyond technical connectivity, interoperability includes syntactic interoperability (shared data formats), semantic interoperability (shared meaning of data), and organizational interoperability (alignment of workflows, responsibilities, and regulatory requirements) [4]. This paper focuses on operational interoperability, defined as the practical ability of clinical trial stakeholders to exchange, interpret, and use data across systems, processes, and sites in routine trial operations.

To make this operational perspective analytically manageable, the paper distinguishes three directions of interoperability. First, same-level or intra-system interoperability concerns data exchange between systems and tools used within a specific task or trial stage. Second, vertical interoperability concerns data exchange across successive stages of the clinical trial lifecycle, for example from recruitment and enrolment to monitoring, intervention and follow-up. Third, horizontal interoperability concerns data exchange across organizations, research sites and, where applicable, countries. This three-level distinction guides both the empirical analysis and the framework presented in the paper.

Despite the availability of these conceptual distinctions and of established interoperability standards, the practical achievement of interoperability remains difficult. Information often remains in data silos, systems cannot always exchange or interpret data smoothly, and organizational or regulatory conditions may restrict data sharing across sites and actors. This raises the need to examine interoperability not only as a technical capability, but also as an operational problem in everyday clinical trial work. Improving operational interoperability can enhance trial efficiency, data quality and the reuse of clinical research data [5].

Against this background, the paper asks: Where do practitioners perceive the main interoperability barriers in digital clinical trials, and how can these barriers be located across same-level, vertical and horizontal forms of data exchange? The paper answers this question through an exploratory qualitative analysis of seven semi-structured interviews with Swiss-based clinical trial stakeholders. Its contribution is twofold: empirically, it identifies recurring operational barriers to data exchange in clinical trial practice; conceptually, it proposes a three-level framework that helps locate interoperability problems within systems, across trial processes and between organizations or sites.

2 Related Work: Interoperability in Digital Clinical Trials

This section reviews literature on digital clinical trials, current modes of data exchange, and interoperability standards. It first outlines how CRI supports digital trial workflows. It then explains how data are currently exchanged across systems, processes and organizations in clinical trials. Finally, it discusses why interoperability problems persist despite the availability of standards such as HL7, FHIR and CDISC ODM. This provides the basis for the research gap and for the three-level analytical framework used in this paper.

2.1 Clinical Research Informatics and Digital Trial Workflows

Healthcare data collection in clinical studies is complex and heterogeneous, spanning the entire study lifecycle from protocol design and regulatory submission to data collection, analysis, and reporting [6]. Clinical trial execution can be divided into three stages: screening and enrolment, intervention and monitoring, and follow-up [7]. These stages include activities such as participant identification, consent management, data capture, intervention delivery, safety assessment, and long-term outcome monitoring.

Digital technologies increasingly support these activities. According to Inan et al. [8], digital clinical trials comprise three main components: digital recruitment and retention, digital health data collection, and data analytics. Digital recruitment includes online consent and participant communication, while digital data collection involves electronic patient-reported outcomes, wearable devices, mobile technologies, and digital biomarkers. Data analytics supports the processing and interpretation of clinical and real-world data.

Clinical trial data are generated from multiple heterogeneous sources, including electronic case report forms, laboratory and imaging systems, surveys, interviews, and web-based patient-reported outcome tools. Electronic data capture systems transform paper-based or locally collected information into computable formats, making data quality, completeness, and security essential for regulatory compliance [7]. Clinical datasets therefore combine demographic, diagnostic, laboratory, imaging, and longitudinal patient-reported data across different systems and study phases [9].

Fig. 1. Interoperability in Digital Clinical Studies

Source: Own, based on adapted from Payne (2019) and Inan et al. (2020)

Figure 1 also illustrates the digital components that increasingly support these trial activities. Inan et al. [8] identify three key elements of digital clinical trials: digital recruitment and retention, digital health data collection, and data analytics. Digital recruitment and retention include online recruitment, online consent and digital communication with participants. Digital health data collection includes electronic patient-reported outcomes, digital biomarkers, wearable technologies and mobile technologies. Data analytics refers to the use of advanced analytical methods for processing and interpreting clinical and real-world data.

2.2 Current Modes of Data Exchange in Clinical Trials

In clinical trial practice, data exchange is facilitated through interconnected systems such as electronic data capture systems, clinical trial management systems, laboratory information systems, electronic health records, and patient-reported outcome platforms. Data transfer may occur through standardized interfaces, structured file exchange, manual re-entry, or reconciliation processes, resulting in a combination of automated, semi-automated, and manual workflows.

Data exchange is required both vertically across sequential trial phases and horizontally between organizations, research sites, sponsors, and countries [6]. Vertical interoperability enables the reuse of data across enrolment, intervention, monitoring, follow-up, and reporting processes, while horizontal interoperability supports multi-site and international studies by extending participant pools and enabling cross-site patient management [10]. However, horizontal exchange also increases complexity due to heterogeneous systems, standards, workflows, and interpretations of regulatory requirements.

Fig. 2. Possibilities and Directions of Data Exchange in Clinical Research

Although standards such as CDISC ODM, HL7, and FHIR provide frameworks for structured data exchange, effective interoperability depends on system compatibility, local implementation practices, vendor configurations, and organizational workflow alignment. Consequently, interoperability is not achieved solely through the existence of standards, but through their consistent implementation in clinical trial processes.

As illustrated in Figure 2 in addition to vertical data interoperability between the sequential stages inside a clinical trial, exchange of data between organizations or sites on a national or even international level is needed. This horizontal data interoperability between multiple sites and countries extends the patient pool, and thus the diversification of clinical data. Also, patients who travel, can participate in a clinical study in different hospitals or research centers without being bound on regional borders [10].

2.3 Standards, Interoperability and Persistent Implementation Gaps

Existing research demonstrates that digital technologies enhance multiple aspects of clinical trial operations, including recruitment, enrolment, data capture, monitoring, remote participation, and patient-centered data collection [10, 11, 12, 13, 14].

Prior studies further emphasize the role of interoperable data exchange systems and standardized frameworks such as CDISC ODM, HL7, and FHIR in supporting syntactic and semantic interoperability across clinical research environments [4, 6, 10, 15, 16].

However, despite the availability of technical standards and digital tools, implementation remains constrained by heterogeneous system landscapes, vendor-specific configurations, local workflows, regulatory requirements, and varying levels of digital maturity across organizations. Consequently, the key challenge is not the existence of standards themselves, but their consistent implementation and operationalization within real-world clinical trial workflows [17].

2.4 Research Gap

Existing research has established the importance of CRI for improving the quality, efficiency and scalability of clinical research ([1,2]). It has also shown that digital tools can support recruitment, enrolment, data capture, monitoring, patient-reported outcomes and remote participation in clinical trials [8, 12, 14]. In parallel, technical work on standards such as CDISC ODM, HL7 and FHIR demonstrates that structured data exchange is possible and that syntactic and semantic interoperability can be supported through shared data models and interfaces [4, 6, 16].

However, a gap remains between the availability of standards and the operational realities of clinical trial practice. Existing studies often focus on specific technical solutions, individual trial components or the general potential of digitalization, while less attention is paid to how practitioners experience interoperability barriers across the full chain of trial work. There is limited empirical insight into how interoperability problems appear simultaneously within systems and tasks, vertically across successive trial processes, and horizontally across organizations, research sites or countries.

This paper addresses this gap by developing an exploratory three-level framework of operational interoperability in digital clinical trials. Rather than evaluating one specific standard or system, the study examines where practitioners locate barriers to data exchange in everyday clinical trial work and how these barriers affect the alignment of technical systems, workflows and organizational interfaces.

2.5 Analytical Framework: Three Levels of Operational Interoperability

Building on the literature reviewed above, the study uses a three-level framework to locate interoperability barriers in digital clinical trials. The framework does not replace established distinctions between technical, syntactic, semantic and organizational interoperability. Instead, it translates these dimensions into three operational directions in which data exchange problems become visible in clinical trial practice.

First, same-level interoperability refers to data exchange between tools, systems or tasks located within the same trial stage or organizational unit. Second, vertical interoperability refers to data exchange across successive clinical trial processes, such as recruitment, enrolment, intervention, monitoring and follow-up. Third, horizontal interoperability refers to data exchange across organizations, research sites, service providers or countries.

Fig. 3. Three levels of operational interoperability in digital clinical trials
- Same level, vertical and horizontal data exchange

These levels are analytically distinct, but they may overlap in practice. For example, a missing API interface may first appear as a same-level technical problem, but it can also create vertical delays across trial stages or horizontal barriers between organizations.

Figure 3 visualizes these three levels. Green arrows indicate functioning or possible data exchange, while red arrows indicate missing, restricted or problematic interfaces. The figure is used as an analytical heuristic for the interview analysis rather than as a complete map of all CRI systems.

3 Methodology to Explore the Topic

A qualitative research design was employed to examine complex workflows and organizational interests in clinical trials. More than 120 international experts were contacted through online clinical trial networks and registries; however, the final sample consisted of seven Switzerland-based participants representing pharmaceutical companies, service providers, healthcare providers, and clinics. Data were collected in 2021 through semi-structured interviews.

The purposive sample was selected to capture variation in organizational roles and involvement across the clinical trial lifecycle, particularly regarding interoperability processes. Specifically, candidates were selected based on their involvement in different processes along the clinical trial lifecycle to gather targeted findings on different levels of interoperability as in Figure 3. Methodologically, the use of a qualitative approach with semi-structured interviews across multiple stakeholder groups such as companies, service providers, healthcare providers, and clinics is appropriate for exploring complex interoperability challenges.

Although the small sample size ($n=7$) limits representativeness, the study provides exploratory insights into interoperability challenges across different stakeholder perspectives. The findings reflect practitioner perceptions at a specific stage of digital clinical trial development and do not address more recent regulatory or AI-related developments. Instead, the analysis focuses on persistent operational barriers, including system compatibility, workflow alignment, customization costs, workarounds, and uncertainty in data exchange.

Interviews were organized into four thematic areas: stakeholder interfaces, process challenges, CRI system applications, and barriers and future aspects of integrated data exchange. Interviews were conducted online, lasted up to 60 minutes, and were analyzed using thematic coding focused on recurring references to systems, standards, interfaces, delays, and cross-site interoperability challenges.

The questions were used flexibly in semi-structured interviews, allowing participants to elaborate on examples from their own organizational context. The analysis focused on recurring references to systems, interfaces, standards, workarounds, delays, customization needs, regulatory uncertainty and cross-site data exchange.

4 Findings

The findings are organized according to the three levels of operational interoperability introduced in Section 2.5: same-level, vertical and horizontal interoperability. The analysis does not quantify the frequency of responses. Instead, it identifies recurring themes across the seven interviews and locates them within the three-level framework.

Themes	Key Insights / Findings	Representative Answer / Quotation of Interviewed Expert
Data Exchange Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many workflows are existent still on paper There are hybrid procedures (paper-based and electronic) Lack or missing data exchange and API interfaces between CRI systems Manual entries and workflows due to missing interoperability 	<p>IQ11 / IN1-7: Manual entries and/or the configuration of an interface, if this is the case, as well as data quality and security count to interoperability challenges on same level</p> <p>IQ11 / IN6: Error sources due to manual entries e.g., from paper and other systems because of missing interfaces are highlighted in terms of data quality</p> <p>IQ12 / IN 1-5: No interface/API to another CRI system in the down-/ upstream interfaces, thus manual data entries as well as specific guidelines of some customers or sponsors</p> <p>IQ12 / IN7: Interruption of workflows because of missing interfaces and commination between CRI systems</p> <p>IQ13 / IN 2-4: Lack of interoperability on horizontal level because of the stand-alone CRI system</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Complexity of API interfaces High variety of workarounds for data exchange due to missing API 	<p>IQ 11 / IN4, 6: Configuration, maintenance, and monitoring of an interface, whether the data is correctly transferred for the sake of quality and correctness of data, as well as interface troubleshooting in case of bugs</p> <p>IQ11-12 / IN5: Resulting variety of workarounds for data exchange e.g. via e-mail due to missing communication between CRI systems</p>
Amount of CRI systems and Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Big amount of data and high number of CRI systems are main challenges 	<p>IQ11-12 / IN5, 7, IQ13 / IN5: High number of co-existing CRI systems and switching between them</p>
Availability of CRI systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Availability of CRI systems and their API interfaces is essential 	<p>IQ11 / IN2: ...configuration of the one API interface with XML, ... its troubleshooting in case of bugs</p>
Customization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No standard, but highly specialized CRI systems 	<p>IQ12 / IN7, IQ13 / IN5: ...and big variety of different, and customized systems used by specific users, institutions, and firms</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High costs for customization, or missing features of standard CRI 	<p>IQ13 / IN5: High costs for specific, and highly customized systems, or missing features of CRI systems with lower costs</p>
Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardization is required 	<p>IQ12 / IN7: Standardization for data, templates, CRI systems is needed - ideally same CRI system used by everyone</p> <p>IQ13 / IN5: Standardization for data, templates, CRI systems is needed, essentially for multi-centric clinical studies taking place in various locations</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variety of standards and not used standardization for data and CRI 	<p>IQ13 / IN7: Different standards and laws for data privacy and cyber security as well as Lack of or not used standardization for data, templates, CRI systems</p>
Data Requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alignment on data structure/format 	<p>IN12 / IN6, IQ13 / IN6-7: Clarification and alignment of requirements between stakeholders on vertical level including using one common data structure/format</p>

Fig. 4. Interoperability Challenges on Different Levels and Directions

Source: Own, based on Interviews

This is important because many barriers mentioned by participants do not belong to one level only. For example, missing API interfaces may first appear as a technical problem within one system environment, but they can also create vertical delays across trial stages and horizontal barriers between organizations or sites. Figure 4 summarizes the main interoperability challenges identified in the interviews. The green layer highlights recurring issues concerning API complexity, workarounds, customization costs, missing functionality in standard systems and inconsistent use of data standards. These issues are discussed below as operational barriers because they connect technical system design with everyday clinical trial workflows.

4.1 Same-Level Interoperability: System Complexity, APIs and Workarounds

At the same level, participants described interoperability barriers that occur within their immediate work environment, particularly where multiple CRI systems must be used for related tasks. These barriers included missing or complex API interfaces, limited compatibility between standard software packages, and the need to manually transfer, copy or re-enter data when systems could not communicate directly. Such workarounds were not described merely as technical inconveniences. They affected documentation time, increased the risk of transcription errors and made users dependent on local knowledge about how to move data between systems.

Participants also pointed to the tension between standard CRI systems and local operational needs. Standard systems may provide basic functionality, but they do not always fit the specific requirements of a trial, organization or workflow. Customization can address this problem, but it may be costly, time-consuming and dependent on vendors or internal IT expertise. Same-level interoperability problems therefore emerge when systems are technically available but not sufficiently aligned with the practical tasks of users.

4.2 Vertical Interoperability: Data Exchange Across Trial Processes

Vertical interoperability barriers became visible when data had to move across successive clinical trial stages. Participants described situations in which data collected during recruitment, enrolment or monitoring could not be smoothly reused in later trial processes without additional formatting, validation or manual intervention. These problems show that interoperability is not only a matter of connecting two systems. It also requires alignment between the data requirements of different trial phases, the timing of data availability, and the responsibilities of actors who manage downstream and upstream processes.

These barriers can create delays and additional coordination work. For example, when data collected in one stage cannot be automatically transferred into the systems used in the next stage, staff may need to export files, reformat data, check data consistency or clarify responsibilities between clinical, administrative and technical actors. Vertical interoperability therefore depends on the continuity of data across the trial lifecycle. It requires that data generated at one point can be interpreted and reused at later stages without losing quality, meaning or regulatory traceability.

4.3 Horizontal Interoperability: Data Exchange Across Organizations & Sites

Horizontal interoperability barriers were particularly evident when data exchange involved different organizations, research sites, service providers or countries. Participants associated these barriers with heterogeneous system landscapes, different organizational procedures, uneven implementation of standards and uncertainty about what can be shared with whom, under which conditions and in which format. Horizontal interoperability therefore depends not only on technical interfaces, but also on organizational trust, shared procedures and compatible interpretations of regulatory requirements.

Cross-site and cross-organizational exchange was described as especially challenging when actors used different platforms, when interfaces were not available, or when data protection and anonymization requirements were interpreted differently. In this study, cross-country exchange primarily refers to intra-European data exchange contexts. The findings should therefore not be generalized to global clinical trial regulation, where data protection, ethics review, infrastructure and organizational practices may differ substantially.

Taken together, the findings show that interoperability barriers are not isolated technical failures. They appear across different operational directions and often connect system-level limitations with process-level delays and organizational uncertainty. The following discussion relates these findings back to existing research and explains why interoperability barriers persist despite the availability of established standards.

5 Discussion

The findings show that operational interoperability problems occur at three interconnected levels. Same-level barriers concern the immediate compatibility of systems, interfaces and local workflows. Vertical barriers concern the movement of data across successive trial processes. Horizontal barriers concern exchange across organizations, sites, service providers and, in some cases, countries. This structure helps specify what is meant by interoperability in clinical trial practice and prevents the concept from remaining too broad or purely technical.

The findings support existing research that identifies interoperability as a central condition for digital clinical research [1, 2, 4]. However, they also show that the existence of interoperability standards does not automatically translate into operational interoperability in clinical trial practice. Standards such as HL7, FHIR and CDISC ODM address important technical, syntactic and semantic aspects of data exchange, but participants' accounts indicate that barriers persist when standards are unevenly implemented, when systems are configured differently by vendors or organizations, when interfaces require costly customization, or when users rely on manual workarounds to bridge incompatible workflows.

This helps explain why poor standardization can persist despite the availability of known solutions. First, standards may exist without being implemented consistently across all systems used in a trial [18]. Second, interoperability often depends on vendor-specific configurations and customized interfaces, which can be costly and difficult to maintain. Third, clinical trial data exchange is embedded in regulated organizational processes, meaning that technical compatibility alone is insufficient if responsibilities, consent conditions, data protection interpretations or quality assurance procedures are not aligned. Fourth, local workarounds can become normalized in daily practice, reducing the immediate pressure to redesign systems even when they generate inefficiencies. The persistence of interoperability barriers is therefore not simply a failure of technical standardization, but an operational problem at the intersection of systems, workflows and organizations.

The three-level framework contributes to this discussion by showing where interoperability problems become visible in practice. Same-level barriers highlight problems within local system environments; vertical barriers reveal breakdowns across the clinical trial lifecycle; and horizontal barriers expose the organizational and regulatory complexity of exchange across sites, providers and countries. This framework is useful because it connects established interoperability dimensions — technical, syntactic, semantic and organizational — with the operational directions in which data must move during clinical trial work.

6 Limitations and Further Research

This study has several limitations. First, the empirical base is small. The analysis draws on seven semi-structured interviews and therefore cannot claim statistical representativeness, data saturation or generalizability across clinical trial contexts. Second, all interviews were conducted with Swiss-based stakeholders. Although participants referred to cross-site and cross-country data exchange, the study primarily reflects an intra-European and Swiss clinical research context. The findings should not be generalized to global clinical trial regulation, where data protection regimes, ethics review procedures, infrastructure and organizational practices may differ substantially. Third, the interviews were conducted in 2021. The study therefore does not assess the most recent regulatory and technological developments, including more recent debates around artificial intelligence in clinical research. Nevertheless, the findings remain relevant because they concern persistent operational barriers: heterogeneous system landscapes, uneven implementation of standards, costly customization, manual workarounds and uncertainty around data exchange responsibilities. Fourth, the sensitivity of the topic affected data collection. Some potential participants were reluctant to discuss organizational challenges, data exchange problems or system limitations in detail. This may have limited the depth of the empirical material. Future research should therefore use a broader sample, include additional countries and stakeholder groups, and combine interviews with document analysis, system mapping or process observation. Comparative research could also test whether the three-level framework developed in this paper applies across different regulatory environments and clinical trial infrastructures.

7 Conclusion

This paper examined operational interoperability in digital clinical trials through an exploratory qualitative study with Swiss-based clinical trial stakeholders. The analysis shows that interoperability barriers do not arise only from missing technical interfaces.

They emerge from the interaction of technical, syntactic, semantic and organizational/procedural conditions that shape how data can be exchanged and reused in practice. The paper's main contribution is a three-level framework that distinguishes same-level, vertical and horizontal interoperability. This framework helps locate where data exchange problems occur within local system environments, across successive clinical trial processes, and between organizations, research sites or countries.

The findings suggest that persistent barriers include complex or missing API interfaces, uneven implementation of standards, costly customization [19], limited functionality of standard CRI systems, manual workarounds and uncertainty around data sharing across organizational or regulatory boundaries [18]. For **practitioners**, the framework can support the identification of interoperability vulnerabilities before they become embedded in trial workflows. For **researchers**, it offers a basis for future comparative studies on how interoperability standards are translated into operational practice. Given the study's small Swiss-based sample, the findings should be read as exploratory rather than generalizable. Nevertheless, they show that improving interoperability in digital clinical trials requires more than adopting technical standards. It requires the coordinated alignment of systems, workflows, responsibilities and organizational conditions across the clinical trial lifecycle.

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